

The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity

"A case Study of Jordanian Private Sector transportation companies located in the Southern region of Jordan. A particular reference is made to the Govern ate of Maan".

Author Details: Mohammed Raja Abulraheem Salah (PhD-Business Administration): Senior lecturer in Administrative and Financial department, Maan University college, Al-Balqa applied University, Maan- Jordan.

ABSTRACT

The Success or failure of modern business organizations depends on the quality of their human resources. Well trained and highly developed employees are considered as corner stone for such success. Hence the purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between training , development, training and development and employees performance and productivity in selected Jordanian Private Sector transportation companies located in the Southern region of Jordan. The study was based on set of hypotheses that H0s: hypothesized no relationships between variables, while H1-H6 hypothesized the existence of relationships between stated variables. A quantitative approach is used Relevant data was collected through structured questionnaire. Subjects for the study consisted of 254 employees which constituted 60% of the total target population of 420 people. 254 structured questionnaire were distributed to employees on job location, 212 questionnaires were returned and only 188 were suitable for statistical analysis. SPSS version 16 has been used to for data analysis. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The statistical tools were aligned with the objective of the research. For this purpose, frequency tables, percentages, means and standard deviations were computed and substantively interpreted. Inferential statistics like Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) and linear regression were used to determine if there is a significant positive relationship existed between the independent variables (training and development) and dependent variables (performance and productivity). The findings indicated that training and development were positively correlated and claimed statistically significant relationship with employee performance and productivity. Analysis and interpretations were made at 0.05 level of significance. The study concluded that training and development have important impact on employee performance and productivity.

Therefore, it was recommended that effective training programs and carefully set development plans should be provided to all employees to enable them to enhance their skills and upgrade their knowledge. Finally, foreseeable future research can be conducted to cover other variables like (capabilities, involvement so on) which might affect performance and productivity.

Keywords: Training, Development, Employees, Performance, Productivity, Transportation Companies.

1. Introduction

Present organizations are facing extensive competition, continuously changing technological and business environment. Globalization and ever changing customer needs have added up more challenges on business organizations. In order to meet these challenges organizations must train and develop their employees. According to [1], current organizations should deal with training necessitates linked up with altering and growing internationalization of industry, diverse national point of view and a varied workforce. So for this purpose individuals are prepared with the right sort of aptitudes, information and capabilities to carry out their allocated responsibilities and therefore training is considered to have a massive impact on organizational efficiency. It is also noticed that more expense in training has led to more productivity. The presence of organizations in a non-static environment forms a constant pressure to maintain superiority in the marketplace. This prompts the need to constantly upgrade employee skills and knowledge and to improve positive work-related attitudes [2]. The method most commonly used to attain these goals is training and development. According to [3] and [4] the objective of training and development, as asserted by them is to develop the skills and competences of employees to improve their performance; to help people grow within the organization in order for the organization to meet its future human resource needs. According to [5], training involves the use of formal and informal processes to impart knowledge and help people acquire the skills necessary for them to perform their jobs satisfactorily, while development prepares

employees for other positions in the organization and increases their ability to move into jobs that may not yet exist. Development therefore is about preparing for change in the form of new jobs, new responsibilities, or new requirements. Therefore, training and development is a necessary effort of a company to improve quality and to meet the challenges of global competition and social change. Providing training and development is one of the many roles of human resource management. This central role has been recognized by many research studies, for instance [6] stressed that employees are a crucial and expensive resource and in order to sustain effective performance, it is important to optimize their contribution to the aims and goals of the organizations. He also went on to say that one major area of the human resource management function of particular relevance to the effective use of human resources is training and development. Within this context

training therefore involves skills acquisition, the process of teaching or learning of skill or job suggested. Training involves an expert working with learning to transfer to them certain areas of knowledge or skill to improve their current jobs. In support for that [7] made the following suggestions firstly: training is any learning activity which is directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task. Secondly: the need for training is as a result of demand of the job and demand of the organization. [8] on the other hand, reviewed training as a systematic process of altering employee's behavior to further organizational goals. It involves improving an employee's skill to the point he or she can do the current job in away to improve organizational performance. Development, according to [9], is any activity which is rather than present needs and which is concerned more with career growth than immediate performance. The extent of development in an organization is to improve employee's conceptual and human skills in preparation for a future job. It is concerned with teaching workers more general skills that will assist them in career growth, thereby equipping them for the future. Manpower development or human resource development According to [10], the existence of unskilled and or skilled humans that need training or re-training to perform specific task in the society. In fact manpower development is focusing on turning out human resource that is needed for effective performance in the organization. Others like[11] see human resource management as the process that seeks to optimize an organizations usage of its human resource. It requires an integrated approach that addresses multidimensional aspects of employees ranging from enhancing technical and interpersonal skills to creative thinking and leaderships. Organization with high productivity or performance levels have made manpower development an integral part of their business culture.

Training and development therefore should be considered not only as opportunity for growth but investment that yield overall returns and benefits to organizations and employees. According to [12], in contributing to the overall goal of the organization, training and development processes are implemented as these benefits will not just the organization but also the individuals making up that organization. For the organization, training and development leads to improved profitability while cultivating more positive attitudes toward profit orientation. For the individuals, training and development improve job knowledge while also helping in identifying with the goals of the organization.

2. Statement of the Problem

The transportation companies referred to in this study are privately owned and they are committed to provide efficient, reliable, unrivalled and quality transportation services to customers. The transportation sector is considered as one of the most important sectors that has a major contribution towards the Jordanian gross national product. Besides that, this sector employs large number of Jordanian citizens specifically in the southern region of Jordan. Currently, employees in these Companies make many mistakes while performing their tasks. These mistakes can affect the quality of transportation services offered to customers and consequently the image of the organization. Managers also were ignorant and misinformed on the need and importance of training and development of manpower in their companies. The success or failure of any business depends on the quality of its human capital and, while it is widely recognized that training and development play important role, there are still many concerns as to which kinds of training , development and skills acquisition bring economic success. More importantly such training and development have to be immediate, quantifiable and applicable to the job nature of these companies. Training and staff development should assist individual performance to impact positively on organizational productivity both in the short

term and in the future. As asserted by [13] performance is associated with quantity of output, quality of output, timelessness of output, presence or attendance on the completed and effectiveness of work completed. Otherwise, Where manpower resources development of an organization is not given the appropriate attention, the implication could be poor organizational performance. [14] Was emphatic that the inability of organizations to attain their goals was as a result of some of poor manpower development policies. Consequently, it becomes necessary to determine how organizational performance can be influenced through manpower training and development. Given the above, it becomes necessary to determine the relationship between training, development, employee performance and productivity in Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the Southern region of Jordan. A particular reference is made to the governate of Maan.

3. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of training and development on employee performance and productivity in Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan. A particular reference is made to the governate of Maan.

4. Objectives of the Research

More specifically, the objectives were stated to:

- 1) Determine the impact of training on employees performance and productivity
- 2) Determine the impact of development on employees performance and productivity
- 3) Explore different methods of training and development that affect employees performance and productivity
- 4) Recommend well structured training process that can be used to improve the training and development at Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan.

4. Study Research Questions

The research questions include the following:

- 1) What is the relationship between training of staff and employees performance and productivity employees?
- 2) What is the relationship between staff development and employees?
- 3) What is the relationship between training & development and employees performance and productivity?
- 4) What are the most used methods of training and development that have effect on employees performance and productivity?

6. Significance of the Study

Training and development is about managing and empowering people, the vital assets of any business or firm. Human resource professionals act as a strategic partner with senior managers and leaders by aligning training and development strategies and practices among others with overall organizational strategies that contribute to an organization's smooth operations. Therefore, understanding human resource practices and particularly Training and development enable managers to help employees perform better in the work and keep them motivated. This in turn will strengthen individual and organizational performance and further the organization's ability to meet its goals according to performance objectives and standards despite internal and external challenges to the organization. The study becomes necessary because many organizations in this contemporary world are striving to gain competitive edge and there is no way this can be achieved without increasing employees' competencies, capabilities, skills etc through adequate training and development designs. However, the study results will help the management to identify the challenges effects of employees' training and development on organizational performance, hence determine the areas where improvements through training and development can be done. It will also help the management in planning

for the development and implementation of effective and efficient training needs that will lead to increased performance and productivity. It is hoped that, the findings of the study will be of great benefit to researchers and scholars or anybody who have interest in this topic. Its findings, may lay a theoretical framework for future empirical study on human resource management practices. This study may be a source of inspiration to other scholars in developing a practical approach of operationalizing human resource management practices.

7. Scope of the Study

It is commonly accepted that the human resource management function of any organization plays a crucial role in the attainment of its goal. Quite a number of practices are undertaken in the human resource management function to ensure the organization attracts and retains competent employees who in turn create an important source of competitive advantage for a firm. The study was conducted to establish the relationship between Training and development as human resource management function and their effect on performance and productivity of Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan . There are many transportation companies but 6 companies were chosen for data collection and the study was conducted to represent the private transportation sector. The target respondents involved in this study were 188 employees selected randomly from these firms. Time, financial resources, geographical representation of transportation companies and limited number of firms were important constraints that affected the conduction of the study.

8. Literature review

Training and Development basically deals with the acquisition of understanding, know-how, techniques and practices. In fact, training and development is one of the imperatives of human resource management as it can improve performance at individual, collegial and organizational levels. As the process of ‘increasing one’s capacity to take action, organizations are now increasingly becoming particular with organizational learning and therefore collective development. According to [15] training and development is beneficial not just for the organization itself but also to the individual employees. On the one hand, training and development leads to improved profitability and produce more positive attitudes toward profit orientation, improves the job knowledge and skills at all levels of the organization, improves the morale of the workforce and helps the employees identify with organizational goals. On the other, training and development benefits individual employees through helping them make better decisions and effective problem solving, assisting in encouraging and achieving self-development and self-confidence, helping an employee a person handle stress, tension, frustration, and conflict, increasing job satisfaction and recognition and moving the person toward personal goals while improving interaction skills [16]. The following insights give a review of relevant literature in a accordance with focused points in this study:

8.1. Insight into Training

The importance of training as a central role of management has been recognized by many research studies. According to [17], the recognition of the importance of training in recent years has been heavily influenced by the intensification of competition and the relative success of organizations where investment in employee development is considerably emphasized. Further researchers added that technological developments, atomization, mechanization, changing environment and organizational change have gradually led some employers to the realization that success relies on the skills and abilities of their employees, and this means considerable and continuous investment in training and development [18] and [19]. Furthermore, the view that human resource management concepts such as commitment to the organization and the growth in the quality movement have led senior management teams to realize the increased importance of training, employee development and long-term education. Such concepts require not only careful planning but a greater emphasis on employee development [20]. Deep reading of literature considers training as the process of improving the existing skills, knowledge, exposure, and abilities in an individual. According to [21], training is an organized increase from the know-how skills and sensations needed for staff members to execute efficiently in the offered process, as well as, to operate in underling situation. Moreover, training

also enhances the capabilities of panel of employees in very effective way by motivating them and transforming them in to well organize and well-mannered, that ultimately affects the performance of organization. [22] defines training as an indicator to enhance superior skills, knowledge, capabilities and outlook of the employees that results in effective performance of the workers. However, he adds one more thing, that is, training extends the production of the organization. In line with this is the believe that training is important mean to improve the employees' productivity which ultimately affects the organization performance and effectiveness [23].

Furthermore,[24] state that the most important impact of training on employees and organization performance is improve the quality and quantity of organization's output, increase in the organization's profitability, safeguarding the organization stability, minimizing the risk, decrease the organization cost and expenses, improving the management of the organization and establishing the organization as national and international entities. All these can be achieved through systematic modification and updating of behavior, skills and abilities to effectively meet future employment aspects. According to [25], research shows that in Europe, 44% of employees receive job-related technical skills training and 33% receive information technology (IT) skills training. 18% of employees have undertaken sales related training in the past year, while 25% have undertaken personnel development skills training, 21% management skills training and 15% leadership skills development. Since training is seen as the most prevalent means for enhancing the individual's productivity and communicating organizational goals to employees, it has to be systematic, well planned and effective. For training programs to be effective, training needs must be identified first. Every training is related to the specific needs of the organization and of the individual employees. It should be launched only after the training needs are assessed clearly. The effectiveness of a training programs can be judged with the help of training needs identified in advance. To identify the same, gap between the existing and required levels of knowledge, skills, performance and aptitudes is to be specified. The problem areas which could be resolved through training should also be identified. In the view of [26] training needs have to be determined first. In this regard, a basic "communication-linking process" between both parties is required. Training must be addressed in such a way that it covers the employees performance-development needs and is in accordance with their job descriptions. Both the employee and the employer have to work together in order to determine what the employees do not know. In addition to the previous arguments, [27] supports a partnership approach between the employees and their companies in determining training needs, as well as the involvement of the employees in setting up training goals. By being involved, employees will not only support the training programs, but their morale will also be enhanced. Besides involvement and participation; both company management and employee must hold shared and collective responsibilities in the employee, training and development process. A After needs assessment, the training objectives must be determined and properly formulated .i.e. who needs training and what training is needed. Then the training is designed and implemented accordingly. Once training needs and objectives are identified, then training programs must be carefully designed and implemented. In this stage, it is very important for the organization to design the training very carefully, the design and implementation of the training should be according to previously determined collective needs. Well designed training programs are more likely to get good results and achieve organizational goals. In line with this is the argument of [28] who claims that according to analysis of the existing literature of different studies that training program should be designed for each job regard to individual, vocational and organization needs. Training programs are the incentives that all employees need to improve their performance and capabilities, therefore increase organizational productivity. Consequently, training should be formed, designed and implemented on the basis of organization specific needs and objectives. Finally, to determine whether objectives are met or not, training programs are subjected to overall evaluation. The evaluation system includes identifying participant reactions to the training process, how much participants learned and how well the participants transfer the training back on their respective jobs; if employees subsequent performance would be better than the previous, then it can be said that the training has a positive impact(most of the time) on employees performance otherwise not [29]. Careful review of literature confirms that the success of training programs depends on the methods of training used by organization. Training methods most commonly used include: on job training, off job training, orientation & induction, technical training programs, foundation training programs refresher, training programs, health & safety training programs, promotional & advancement training programs, remedial training programs and laboratory training programs. According to [30], training

and development training techniques are classified into behavioral or On-the-job (orientations, job instruction training, apprenticeships, internships and assistantships, job rotation and coaching) and cognitive or off-the-job (Lectures, computer-based training, games and simulations etc. These tend to influence employees' performance and organizational competitiveness.

When selecting among training methods, the following factors must be considered as they highly contribute to the effectiveness of training programs :such factors include: objectives of training, cost of training, time of training, location of training, frequency of training, suitability of training methods, content of training, delivery style, capability of application, trainer's capabilities and employees willingness to" learn and apply". According to [31], the trainer's role is shifting from a simple role of providing skills to active communicator, who makes an effort in achieving training as well as organizational objectives. Trainer plays an important role in transferring the learning to work. The one of the barriers to convey the training to the employees is "poor training content and delivery style". Thus a good trainer is the one who has the skills to conduct a training program more purposeful by setting an appropriate training objectives, capture the attention of the audience and also deliver it in the best way so the employee can easily understand because training objectives are considered as the 'pillar' of training programs and lack of solid objectives leads to failure of training programs. To conclude, the benefits of well maintained training programs can be summed up as: Improves morale of employees, training helps the employee to get job security and job satisfaction. The more satisfied the employee is and the greater is his morale, the more he will contribute to organizational success and the lesser will be employee absenteeism and turnover. Less supervision, a well trained employee will be well acquainted with the job and will need less of supervision. Thus, there will be less wastage of time and efforts. Fewer accidents, errors are likely to occur if the employees lack knowledge and skills required for doing a particular job. The more trained an employee is, the less are the chances of committing accidents in job and the more proficient the employee becomes. Chances of promotion, employees acquire skills and efficiency during training. They become more eligible for promotion. They become an asset for the organization. Increased productivity, training improves efficiency and productivity of employees. Well trained employees show both quantity and quality performance. There is less wastage of time, money and resources if employees are properly trained [32].

8.2. Insight into Development

The focus of human resource development is on developing the most superior workforce which helps the organization for successive growth..This can only be achieved through proper and systematic implementation of employee training and development programs. Employees are always regarded with development in career-enhancing skills which leads to employee motivation and retention. There is no doubt that a well trained and developed staff will be a valuable asset to the company and thereby will increase the chances of their efficiency and effectiveness in discharging their duties. Training is a learning experience which has a capacity to make positive changes and reach up to the desired objectives of the organization. It improves the ability of the employee to perform the job efficiently and with excellence [33]. Development, on the other hand means those learning opportunities designed to help employees to grow. Development is not primarily skills oriented. Instead it provides the general knowledge and attitudes, which will be helpful to employers in higher positions. Efforts towards development often depend on personal drive and ambition. Development activities such as those supplied by management development programs are generally voluntary in nature. Development provides knowledge about business environment, management principles and techniques, human relations, specific industry analysis and the like is useful for better management of a company [34]. Development programs are regarded as specific framework for helping employees to develop their personal and professional skills, knowledge, attitudes, behavior and consequently improve their abilities to perform specific task in the organization.

[35] is of opinion that manpower development could be seen as organization specific. This is because it is largely a function of organization manpower needed or job specification. It is adoption of the human resource available in the country to the need or objectives and orientation of a given organization. In fact manpower development focused on turning out human resource that is needed for effective performance in the organization [36]. It is geared towards updating workers with new techniques or skills associated with the performance of their jobs [37]. According to [38] manpower development methods includes under study,

job rotation, self-development and self-assessment. Under-study is good for succession planning because it allows smooth transition of work when one officer leaves a schedule or the organization. Job rotation involves workers moving from one schedule to the other within the same organization to allow for competence on all spheres of work while self-development means a personal desire to improve through an individual's attempt to embark on study and practical experience that are independent of an organization's role and contribution. Self-assessment means personal identification of strength and an attempt to improve and build current efforts for a more fulfilling corporate movement.

Other methods of manpower development include orientation, on-the-job training, in service training, committee/work group method, vestibule training method and apprenticeship, coaching/understanding, job rotation, committee membership, special assignment, programmed instructions, simulation, special course, professional bodies membership, business games and part-time programs [39]. Further methods of employee development include: career planning, mentoring, job training, and proficiency courses such as technical courses and professional certifications to improve the current and future job performance of employees. It also involves existence of a cordial atmosphere in organizations that encourage employees to add value to themselves to enhance their current and future goal attainment in a cost effective ways. No matter what method of employee development is used; what counts is that employee development programs should be designed to meet specific objectives, which contribute to both employee and organizational effectiveness. Within this context, there are several steps in the process of management development which ought to be mentioned. These steps includes reviewing organizational objectives, evaluating the organization's current management resources, determining individual needs, designing and implementing development programs and evaluating the effectiveness of these programs, measuring the impact of training on participants quality of work life and finally, providing effective feedback that lists the overall returns and benefits on employees and organization. Human resource management is an area that needs to be creative in designing and running employees development programs. [40] suggested that if the training and development function is to be effective in the future and yields all expected returns, it will need to move beyond its concern with techniques and traditional roles. He describes the strategic approaches that the organization can take to training and development, and recommends that the choice of approach should be based on an analysis of the organization's needs, management and staff attitudes and beliefs, and the level of resources that can be committed. This more strategic view-point should be of use in assessing current efforts as well as when planning for the future.

8.3. Insight into Training and Development

Vast amount of published research has highlighted the types of relationship that exists between training, deployment and common organizational measures like performance, productivity, competitive edge and effectiveness. In this study, the researcher concentrated more on the ties and links in between that brings together the concepts of training and deployment and then determines the impact of these combined concepts on performance and productivity. According to [41], training and development should be seen not only as the thread that ties together all human resource practices, but also as the instrument for establishing and signaling when and how work practices should change. In other words, employees should take on the role of organizational change agents. To be effective in this role, the human resource manager will need to create a framework for making human resource decisions based on Accra Polytechnic vision and strategic plan. In line with the above is that, training helps an individual learn how to perform his present job satisfactorily which involves developing the individual or employee for a future job and growth of the individual in all respects. In short, development complements training because human resources can exert their full potential only when the learning process goes far beyond simple routine [42].

When brought together training and development is considered as very essential part of the human resource department in any organization. [43] claims that training is the process of teaching, informing, or educating people so that they may become as well qualified as possible to do their job, and become qualified to perform in positions of greater difficulty and responsibility. The staff in an organization is trained in different areas so that they become efficient in performing their activities. In service training is provided to employees so that their performance in the job increases as well as equips them to hold the responsibilities well. This training provides a development and growth for the individual through acquiring new core

competencies and capabilities. From the above literature reading one can easily extract the existence, linkage and depth of relationship between training and development and employees performance. In his research [44] states that, there exist a relationship between training and development and employee performance. Training is the method of learning new things through education, practice and experience. While development will make the employees to have more awareness and readiness regarding the requirements and requisites of expected future jobs and hence prepare them effectively that is develop them in away to be mature enough to contribute to the achievement of organizations goals.

Recent research papers, such as [45] concluded that, training and development are indispensable strategic tools for effective individual and organization performance, thus, organization are spending money on it with confidence that it will earn them a competitive advantage in the world of business. However, for any organization to achieve its stated goals and objective in this competitive world, adequate and relevance training and development of staff cannot be over emphasized. Organization are expected to identify training need of its employees and design training programs that will eventually help to optimally utilize their workforce towards actualization of organization objective [46].

Deep reading of literature on the subject of training and development has made the researcher to notice that, some people still cannot differentiate between training and development and therefore approach this issue with same mentality. This of course deprive the organizations from benefiting from training and development returns. This argument is supported by the work of [47] in which they said that training and development may probably mean the same thing to a lot of people because they both lead to the improvement of an individual productivity in an organization but there are some significant differences. Training means to educate someone normally, mainly by instruction, drill, and discipline. It is regarded as applying principally to the improvement of skills and hence to learning how to perform specific tasks. In contrast, development emphasizes an unfolding process of bringing to an advanced state; significant consequence of continuous growth, progress and innovativeness. In combining training and development organizations may benefit in so many ways: for example researchers like [48] observed the usefulness of training and development in an organization and identified the functions of training as follow: it increases productivity; improves the quality of work; enhances skills, knowledge, understanding and attitude; engenders the use of tools and machine; reduces waste, accidents, turnover, lateness, absenteeism and other overhead costs; eliminates obsolescence in skills, technologies, methods, products, capital management; enhances the implementation of new policies and regulations; prepares people for achievement, improves manpower development and ensures the survival and growth of the enterprise. Training and development helps in optimizing the utilization of human resource that further helps to achieve the organizational goals as well as their individual goals. Training and development helps to provide an opportunity and broad structure for the development of human resources' technical and behavioral skills in the organization. It also helps the employees in attaining personal growth. Training and development helps in increasing the job knowledge and skills of employees at each level. Training and development as a unified concept helps to expand the horizons of human intellect and an overall personality of the employees. Training and development is the framework for helping employees to develop their personal and organizational skills, knowledge, and abilities. The focus of all aspects of human resource development is on developing the most superior workforce so that the organization and individual employees can accomplish their work goals in service to the general public [49]. According to [50] Investing in training and development is imperative for any organization, which will certainly realize a return on investment in training and developing their workers. Those who neglect this important aspect of human resource management are bound to suffer major consequences of falling behind in today's competitive marketplace; that is to say When companies fall behind in the training and development of their human resources, they are prone to fall behind in countless other ways as well.

Despite the above mentioned benefits; and in reality many of used training and development programs do not yield their expected returns. The practical explanations for failure may include the following : [51] points out that many employers are opposed to training and development initiatives because they assume that the responsibility for training people to be workers falls on the school system, not on firms. In addition, they consider that it is the responsibility of the employees to learn how to do their job so that they are hired. Furthermore, they regard training and development programs as an expense which it is difficult to convince

shareholders to approve. According to the perspective of the researcher, if aligned with the goals, mission and objective of the organization, and supported by both the employer and the employee, training, development and education programs delivered the right way and at the right time provide substantial returns for the employer in terms of increased productivity, knowledge, loyalty and profit. Other reasons of failure are outlined in the studies of [52] and [53], according to these studies the first reason identified for the failure of training and development program stems from the training objectives not being aligned with the business needs. If the root of the problem of poor performance, for instance, it is related to factors such as reward systems, job design and motivation, which are not related to training, training will be pointless. Secondly, in the absence of objectives to provide direction and focus, training will certainly not succeed. Training and development should include a focused process that allows the employee to ponder desired results. Objectives afford important direction and focus for learning the final product, which is a change in job performance. Thirdly, perspective researchers also hold that when training is too expensive if compared to its short-term return on investment, then companies may consider it a failure and, therefore, unacceptable. However, the long-term pay-off may be rewarding. Fourthly, training will be worthless if the participants regard the training program as a mere event without any change to their behavior. Whenever training is considered as a single event, the chances of behavior change are slim. Fifthly, training is also likely to fail if participants are not held accountable for the results. Generally, employees are not held accountable for the use of the contents of their course in the workplace. Unless they are held accountable, no change will occur in their behavior. Sixthly, if the conditions are not conducive to learning, the training efforts will have been in vain. In this instance without the support of line management training will also fail. When there is no support from direct managers and supervisors, the employees will resist implementing the new skills and knowledge acquired during the training course. Management involvement is crucial to the learning process. Another reason for the failure of training and development occurs when the company fails to isolate the effects of training and development. However, other factors rather than training may influence performance. Thus, the advances directly related to training must be isolated. If not, some training programs clearly noticeable as impacting on the bottom line may be discarded as irrelevant. For the success of a training program, top executives' commitment is critical. Top management will not only allocate resources but, for the training and development to succeed, will also participate in the design of the process. Lastly, training and development will be unsuccessful if there is a failure to provide feedback and use information about results. If the company fails to evaluate training by providing feedback, employees will not be able to know about their progress, nor facilitators to understand the success of their programs. Still these causes of failure can be prevented or at least reduced. [54] suggested set of desirable techniques and models which may prevent the failure of a training program. The study concluded that the organizations should choose those models of training and development that successfully fit into the organization's culture. Needs of training and essential business skills should be carefully assessed. Then appropriate managerial techniques as well as the comprehensive plans or models should be implemented for the effective training and development program in order to motivate the employees, reduce the performance gaps and achieve the organizational goals effectively.

8.4. Insight into Performance and Productivity

Training and development plays an important role in human resource development to achieve both objectives of the individuals and the organization. Training and development is said to have significant impact on employees performance as well as organizational performance. In general, the term performance is a broader based concept which includes effectiveness, efficiency, economy, quality, consistency behavior and normative measures. According to [55], the definition of performance is the achievement of specific task which is measured against predetermined standards of accuracy, completeness, speed and cost. He also added that, in an employment contract, performance is considered to be an achievement of the employee commitment that releases the performer from all liabilities that is designed under the contract. Efficiency and effectiveness are major components of performance, which can be emphasized through training and development to increase performance of individual .

Organizational performance on the other hand can also be defined as the organization's ability to attain its goals by using human resources in an effective and efficient manner. Hence the success or failure of business organizations depends on employees performance. According to [56], effective employee training leads to the following benefits: an increase in quality goods and services as a result of potentially fewer mistakes. Consequently, accuracy, effectiveness, good work, safety practices and good customer service can be expected. An intelligent and well-trained workforce is central to both productivity and the success of an organization. Organizations can save money by retaining valuable employees: the costs of recruitment and training of new entrants can be avoided due to lower levels of employees turnover. In line with this theme, is the work of [57] in which they said that, training giving to employees will results in increasing the level of satisfaction of their current jobs. This according to them underlines the needs of company to concentrate on building employee capability and development to achieve job satisfaction.

Productivity can be defined as an overall measure of the ability to produce a good or service. More specifically, productivity is the measure of how specified resources are managed to accomplish timely objectives as stated in terms of quantity and quality [58]. Training and development can be regarded as the major factor in the creation of employee human capital, which determines the long-term productivity of an employee's behavior [59]. Similar to this is the study of [60] in which he examined the role of training and development as a prominent determinant for improving human resource productivity. He employed questionnaires and personal interview with human resource managers; and training and placement officers. He found in his study that training and development plays a very important role in improving the productivity of human resources. Other researchers like [61] observed the usefulness of training and development in an organization and identified the functions of training as follow: it increases productivity; improves the quality of work; enhances skills, knowledge, understanding and attitude; engenders the use of tools and machine; reduces waste, accidents, turnover, lateness, absenteeism and other overhead costs; eliminates obsolescence in skills, technologies, methods, products, capital management; enhances the implementation of new policies and regulations; prepares people for achievement, improves manpower development and ensures the survival and growth of the enterprise. Furthermore [62] were of the opinion that effective training would not only equip employee with most of the knowledge and skills needed to accomplish jobs, it would also help to achieve overall organization objectives by contributing to the satisfaction and productivity of employee. Sometimes, the above argument may not stand correct. Here researchers like [63] is of the view that an organization may have employees with the ability and determination, with appropriate equipment and managerial support yet productivity could still fall below expected standards. This missing link is often caused by the lack of acquisition and by extension utilization of adequate skills and knowledge as well as positive work attitude by employees, which are normally acquired through effective mechanism of manpower training and development. Absence of such staff training and development programs in an organization often manifests tripartite problems of incompetence, inefficiency and ineffectiveness and consequently negatively contributing to individual and firms activities. A note worth mentioning in this respect is that [64] postulates that training and development is not exclusively reserved for newly recruited staff but also it is a necessity for the older employees. Therefore, for the purpose of enhancing individual performance, it is important that training and development be made a continuous process that should last through an employee's entire working life. The presence of a continuous training and development according to [65] can solve a variety of manpower problems which militate against optimal productivity and performance. These problems include needs to: increase productivity and efficiency, improve the quality and quantity of work, Boost employees' morale and organizational climate, implement new or changed policies or regulations, ensure the survival and growth of the organization, develop new skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes, provide for succession plan and ensure continuity of leadership, prevent skill obsolescence and cope with the new technological advancement, use correctly new tools, machines, processes, methods or modifications thereof, reduce waste, accidents, turnover, lateness, absenteeism, and other overhead costs and bring incumbents to that level of performance which meets "100 percent of the time" the standard of performance for the job. Therefore, one can conclude that training provide adequate criteria to an individual to perform better in a given task and subsequently contributes to the firm performance. Highly developed, intelligent, flexible, skilled, competent, effective and well trained workforce is central to performance, productivity and the success of organizations.

9. Research Theoretical Framework

General human capital theories support the tendency towards investment in training and development because such investment is considered very beneficial for the performance and productivity of employees, and performance of the organization as a whole. The research framework in this study is drawn graphically based on the grounds of literature review that the researcher has carried out. Here it is theorized that the independent variables, training and development had a positive effect on the dependent variables performance and productivity of employees, and on performance of the organization as a whole.. Figure (1) below shows the research framework of this study.

Figure (1): Research Theoretical Framework

10. Hypotheses of the Study

Hypothesis development is very important because acceptance and the rejection of hypothesis show the significance of the study. On the basis of literature review and the above theoretical frame work the hypotheses of this study are taken as follows:

Set One hypotheses

Ho: "There is not a significance relationship between employees training and employees performance ".

H1: "There is a significant relationship between employees training and employees performance ".

Ho: "There is not a significance relationship between employees development and employees performance ".

H2: "There is a significant relationship between employees development and employees performance ".

Ho: "There is not a significance relationship between employees training & development and employees performance ".

H3: "There is a significant relationship between employees training & development and employees performance ".

Set Two hypotheses

Ho: "There is not a significance relationship between employees training and productivity ".

H4: "There is a significant relationship between employees training and productivity ".

H₀: "There is not a significance relationship between employees development and productivity ".

H₅: "There is a significant relationship between employees development and productivity ".

H₀: "There is not a significance relationship between employees training & development and productivity ".

H₆: "There is a significant relationship between employees training & development and productivity ".

11. Research Methodology

11. 1.Research Design

This study utilized the survey research design method and quantitative approach is used. For this purpose, structured questionnaires were used as the survey instrument. The quantitative research is that which tries to find answer to a question through analysis of quantitative data, i.e., the data shown in figures and numbers. Generally speaking, quantitative research gives the researches the opportunities to interact and gather data directly from their research participants to understand a phenomenon from their perspectives. In this case the logic of using this approach is to maintain real life references and phenomena regarding the impact of employees training and development on employees performance and productivity. In addition to that the chosen method is known for its economies in terms of time and resources. Finally, the employment of quantitative approach is compatible with the study problems and its questions; and it enables the current study to reach and collect empirical evidence from a wider group of population.

11. 2.Target Population

According to [66], a “population” relates to the entire set of data that is of interest to the researcher, and the “target population” refers to the group of people or objects from which the sample should be taken. Because it is not feasible to collect data for the entire statistical population, a sample, which is a representative of the population, was drawn from the employees of transportation companies. Based on that, the target population is 420 people, and it includes all full time employees of the Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan. The population comprise managers, technical officers, supervisors, administrative staffs, secretaries, archives, accountants, logistics staffs and office assistants, drivers and support staff were targets of the study. The target population characteristics is summarized as shown in table (1).

Table(1): The Target Population Characteristics

Sequence	Name of Transportation firms	Population	Percentage %
1	A	102	24
2	B	90	21
3	C	76	18
4	D	66	16
5	E	58	14
6	F	28	7
Total	(A-F)	420	100

Source: Prepared by the researcher 2016

11. 3.Study Sample Size

Sample size is referred to the appropriate number of respondents chosen for the study, and it is extracted from the total target population of employees working for these companies. From the above target population a sample of 60% of the respondents was selected from within each company in proportion that

each company bears to the study population. Therefore, the sample size of the study reached to 254 respondents. This translates to 60% of the study population and has sufficiently surpassed the minimum threshold sample size of 10% suggested by [67] 30% is considered acceptable by [68] and [69] and a sample size of 30 (sampling at least 10% of the target population) for a small population as proposed by [70]. Calculation of representative sample given the target population is shown in table(2).

Table(2): Calculation of Representative Sample

Sequence	Name of Transportation Companies	Frequency	Sample Ratio	Sample Size
1	A	102	0.60	62
2	B	90	0.60	54
3	C	76	0.60	46
4	D	66	0.60	40
5	E	58	0.60	35
6	F	28	0.60	17
Total	(A-F)	420	0.60	254

Source: Prepared by researcher 2016

10. 4.Research instrument

In this study two instruments are used for the collection of relevant data:

11/4(a): Primary Data : primary data is collected through the use of well structured questionnaire that contain relevant questions regarding training, development, employee performance and productivity in these companies. The questionnaire used to allow the response of the respondents in a standard direct way, unbiased approach and objective oriented. The use of questionnaire provides the information to be presented in a numeric way. Despite of questionnaire method benefits; questionnaire method has several limitations, for example lackadaisical attitude of respondents, non-attendance and lack of cooperation. This instrument of research is referred for external judgment to ensure validity. The questionnaire comprises five sections:

Section(1): comprising eight(8) items seeking demographic data such as gender, age, nationality, education, occupational status or category, experience and income.

Section(2): consist of ten(10) items which sought to collect information about the impact of training methods on employees performance and productivity.

Section(3): consist of twelve (12) items. which sought to collect information about the impact of development methods on employees performance and productivity.

Section(4): consist of three(03) items requesting information about employees performance.

Section(5): consist of eleven(11) items requesting information about employees productivity. Instrument Items in Sections (2-5) are shown in table (3).

Table(3) : Instrument Items For Seeking Information

Training Methods			Development Methods		
Section	Item #	Description	Section	Item #	Description
2	1	On Job Training	3	1	Formal Education Programs
	2	Off Job Training		2	Behavioral & Self assessment Programs
	3	Orientation & Induction		3	Enrich Job Experience
	4	Technical Training Programs		4	Scheduled Effective Feedback
	5	Foundation Training Programs		5	Train The Trainers Programs
	6	Refresher Training Programs		6	Enhancement & Job Satisfaction Program
	7	Health & Safety Training Programs		7	Effective Participation in Setting Development Programs
	8	Promotional & Advancement Training Programs		8	Career Development & Progression Programs
	9	Remedial Training Programs		9	Development Of Leadership Traits
	10	Field Training Programs		10	Membership Of Work & Professional Committees
			11	Simulation & Special Assignments	
			12	Job Rotation & Challenging Job Transfers	
Performance			Productivity		
Section	Item #	Description	Section	Item #	Description
4	1	Result –Oriented Measures (Criterion –Based): a) Effectiveness b) Efficiency c) Economy d) Quality	5	1	Improved Quality: a) Project b) Products c) Service
	2	Relative-Normative Measures: a) Concepts b) Instruments c) Applications		2	Less Defects, Failure & Malfunctions
	3	Predetermined Standards: a) Accuracy b) Completeness c) Cost d) Speed		3	Reduction of Staff Turnover & Absenteeism
				4	Minimum Control and Supervision needs
		5		Opportunity For Growth & Progress	
		6		Improved Employees Behavior	
		7		Competitive Edge Attainment	
		8		Good Customers Service	
		9		Waste Reduction	
		10		Improved Working Conditions	
		11		Improved Company Image	

Source: Prepared by researcher 2016

11/4(b): Secondary Data : secondary sources include all relevant available data that have been prepared, collected, and analyzed by others which include research publications, periodicals, essays, standard records, evaluation reports and other relevant documentaries.

11/5 Validity and Reliability

According to common knowledge research principles an instrument is valid if it measures what it is intended to measure and accurately achieves the purpose for which it was designed. To ensure validity of the instrument, face, and content; the questionnaire was given to professionals for judgment, appropriateness and over all evaluation. Reliability, on the other hand relates to the consistency of collected information. In order to maintain the reliability of the instrument used a pilot study was carried out on a sample of forty five (45) employees of Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan . The responses of respondents were scored and the result of the reliability test was 0.821 showing that the instrument used in this study is regarded as sound, consistent and reliable.

11/6 Data collection

The numbers of questionnaires distributed to the respondents is 254, which account to 60% of the total target population of 420 people. The total number of returned questionnaires is 212. Returns were subjected to a careful checking and 24 questionnaires were excluded and regarded as unsuitable for statistical analyses because they do not meet the conditions and criteria of answering and filling the questionnaires, therefore, the total number of useable returns is 188. None response is 42 and it was assumed that the non-respondents were either unwilling to cooperate or simply not interested in the survey. Summary of distributed, returned, useable, non responses questionnaires are shown in table (4).

Table (4): Summary of Distributed, Returned, Useable, Non responses Questionnaires

Condition	Distributed Questionnaires		Returned Questionnaires		Useable Questionnaires		Un- Useable Questionnaires		Non -Response	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Number of employees	254	100	212	83	188	74	24	9	42	17

Source: Prepared by researcher 2016

11/7 Procedures

The empirical data for the study were collected through a well-structured questionnaire (with 36 items) , which was distributed among the employees of Jordanian Private Sector transportation companies located in the Southern region of Jordan. Simple instructions and assistance were given on how to correctly fill in the questionnaires and confidentiality of information is assured. The scoring of responses is carried out as follows:

Section (1): No scores were attached (i.e. bio- data)

Sections(2-3-4-5): Contain both independent and dependent variables. Respondents were required to provide their rating on their perception using a Five point Likert scale (5-Strongly Agree, 4-Agree, 3- Undecided, 2- Disagree,1- Strongly Disagree). This scale best describes the extent to which the respondents agree with each items in the questionnaire. The mean rating of response to questionnaire items is shown in table (5).

Table (5): Mean Rating of responses to questionnaire items

Response Category	Abbreviation	Points	Bounding Unit
Strongly Agree	(SA)	5	4.50 - 5.00
Agree	(AG)	4	3.50 - 4.49
Undecided	(UN)	3	2.50 - 3.49
Disagree	(DI)	2	1.50 - 2.49
Strongly Disagree	(SD)	1	1.00 - 1.49

Source: Prepared by researcher 2016

In order to ensure completeness and logical consistency of responses, data editing was carried out each day by the researcher. Identified mistakes and data gaps were rectified as soon as possible. Once editing was done with, the data were analyzed using quantitative techniques. Data analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version16). The use of this package is made with the intension to produce both descriptive and inferential Statistics. The summary of result was presented using frequency distribution and percentages, which was used to determine the proportion of respondents choosing the various responses. Tables, charts and graphs can be used to ensure easy understanding of the analyses. Inferential Statistics such as Pearson Correlation, and Linear Regression statistical model were used to identify and evaluate the causal relationship between dependent and independent variables and to test the hypotheses of the study.

12.Data Analysis and Main Findings

12.1 Respondents Demographic Profile

Table 6: Frequency Distribution For Respondents Demographics

Sequence	Demographic item	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	Gender				
	Male	170	90.42	90.42	90.42
	Female	18	09.58	09.58	100
2	Age				
	less than 20	16	08.51	08.51	08.51
	21-30	54	28.72	28.72	37.23
	31-40	64	34.04	34.04	71.27
	41-50	42	22.34	22.34	93.61
	above 50	12	06.38	06.38	100
3	Marital Status				
	Married	126	67.02	67.02	67.02
	Not Married	42	22.34	22.34	89.36
	Engaged	20	10.64	10.64	100
4	Nationality				
	Jordanians	117	62.23	62.23	62.23
	Syrians	20	10.63	10.63	72.86
	Iraqis	10	05.32	05.32	78.18
	Sudanese	14	07.44	07.44	85.62
	Yeminis	12	06.38	06.38	92.00
	Asians	14	08.00	08.00	100
5	Education Level				
	Primary	22	11.70	11.70	11.70
	Secondary	128	68.10	68.10	79.80
	Diploma	21	11.17	11.17	90.97
	Bachelor	12	06.38	06.38	97.35
	H. Diploma	3	01.60	01.60	98.98
	Masters	2	01.10	01.10	100
6	Occupation Status				
	CEOs	6	03.19	03.19	03.19
	Operation Manger	12	06.38	06.38	09.57
	HR. Mangers	6	03.19	03.19	12.76
	Supervisors	12	06.38	06.38	19.14
	Support Staff	24	12.76	12.76	31.90
	Other Workers (Drivers)	128	68.10	68.10	100
7	Experience				
	1-3 years	35	18.61	18.61	18.61
	4-6 years	42	22.34	22.34	40.95
	7-10 years	60	31.92	31.92	72.87
	above 10 years	51	27.12	27.12	100
8	Monthly Income				
	Below 399	55	29.25	29.25	29.25
	400- less than 599	72	38.29	38.29	67.59
	600-less than 799	30	15.95	15.95	83.49
	800-less than 999	19	10.10	10.10	93.59
	above 1000	12	6.41	6.41	100
Total	--	188	100	100	100

Table 6 above gives the following statistical demographic indications:

- a) **With respect to Gender**, table 6 indicates the gender allocation of the sample of respondents from Jordanian Transportation companies at which the research was conducted. As can be seen from the table above the representation of male is 170(90.42 %) and female representation is 18(9.58%). The explanation for this tendency is that, the natures of transportation jobs (specially long distance driving) does not suit females because driving jobs normally done by men drivers and normally stay remote from their homes or place of residence. In addition to that, the Jordanian culture and traditions do not allow Women to work in male dominated companies and a void them working in such harsh working conditions.
- b) **With respect to Age**, table 6 indicates that the majority of participants age is between 31-40 (34.04%); then comes the age between 21-30(28.72%);then the age between 41-50(22.34%); next comes the age less than 20(08.51%) and above 50(06.38%). Careful analysis of age distribution shows that, these companies prefer to employ young able bodies because the nature of work requires people that have stamina and take the burden of heavy load jobs. There has been an ongoing debate as to whether a young work force could positively affect productivity in a company. According to [71] this group of employees are “independent entrepreneurial thinkers who relish responsibility, demand immediate feedback, and expect a continuous sense of accomplishment.” They are regarded as the drivers of firms profitability and therefore, they are essential to the growth of every company.
- c) **With respect to Marital Status**, table 6 indicates that married workers 126(67.02%); not married 42(22.34%); and engaged 20(10.64%). The Classification of majority of respondents as married benefited this study in that, the respondent took serious interest in the survey by filling and returning these questionnaires to the best of their ability because they connected this study on training and development with potential increase in financial rewards and improvement in their social status.
- d) **With respect to Nationality**, table 6 indicates that the majority of respondents were Jordanian citizens 117(62.23%); while other nationalities 71(37.77%). These percentages indicate that these companies meet labor law requirements regarding the employment of Jordanian citizens and the accepted proportion of expatriates working in these companies (Jordanization of Jobs).
- e) **With respect to Education**, table 6 indicates that most respondents had secondary education 128(68.10%); primary education 22(11.70%); while minority of the rest of respondents 38 (20.20%) hold higher degrees ranging from diplomas to masters. The findings give clear indication that these kinds of jobs do not require highly educated people; and technical expertise is required to handle tasks and responsibilities assigned to them.
- f) **With respect to Occupational Status**, table 6 indicates that the majority of employees are drivers 128(68.10%) assisted by 24(12.76%) support staff ; supervised by 12(06.38%) supervisors; and managed by 12(06.38%) middle management, human resource managers 6(03.19) and top management CEOs 6(03.19) . These analysis give clear indication that the type of structure used in these companies is hierarchal one and the majority of employees are found in the lower level of the hierarchy.
- g) **With respect to Experience**. table 6 indicates that the majority of employees 60(31.92%) have between 7-10 years of experience; 51(27.12%) respondents have above 10 years of experience; 42(22.34%) respondents have 4-6 years of experience and only 35(18.61%) respondents have 1-3 years of experience. Analyzing this pattern of experience give clear indication that the experience of those workers in the transportation industry goes beyond 10 years. Findings on the years of experience suggested that these companies have high level of staff retention. This is in line with [72] findings that the human resource manger has encouraged hard work and more employee retention in the company. The company also has a salary and bonus structure based on employee longevity and performance. Despite claims made by the company, there are other factors, which can encourage employees to stay long in the company. The work environment, qualities of relationships that employees create are all factors that motivate employees to stay on in a company. Fear of the unknown also plays a key role as employees are not sure as to what awaits them in their new job.

h) **With respect to income**, table 6 indicates that the majority of employees 72(38.29%) earn between 400-599 (JD) per month; 55(29.25) earn below 399(JD) per month; 30(15.95%) of respondents earn between 600-799 (JD) per month;19(9.6%) of respondents earn between 800-999 (JD) per month; and finally 12(6.41%) of respondents earn above 1000 (JD) per month. Careful insight into these levels of earnings show that the level of income is still low compared to the same industry in neighboring countries; that's why management of these private companies need to reassess their pay structure or provide a system of extra rewards which might balance out these difference.

12.2 Reliability Analysis

This part presents the background information of the respondents; findings of the analysis are based on the objectives of the study that identifies the impact of training and development on employee performance and productivity. The study targeted a sample size of 254 respondents and from which 188 questionnaires were considered as relevant for statistical analysis reaching a response rate of 74%. This response rate was satisfactory to make conclusions on the effect training and development on employee performance and productivity. After that the responses of respondents were scored and the reliability of the tool was determined using Cronbach's Alpha. Accordingly, when reliability values of questionnaire items are more than alpha value then it indicate that the scale can be considered consistent, sound and reliable. For the sake of internal consistency, soundness and reliability, SPSS (version 16) was used to carry out reliability analysis. Cronbach's Alpha reliability analysis are shown in table 7.

Table (7): Reliability Analysis

SN	Scale	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Training Methods	10	0.843
2	Development Methods	12	0.832
3	Performance	03	0.828
4	Productivity	11	0.813

In general, a higher value shows a more reliable generated scale. According to [73] 0.70 is an acceptable reliability coefficient. In table 7, the reliability values of the stated variables (ranges from 0.813 to 0.843) are greater than the prescribed threshold of ($\alpha=0.70$) and in comparison Cronbach's Alpha values are compatible to reliability test of the conducted pilot study with Cronbach's Alpha value ($\alpha=0.821$); hence the scale is sound and reliable.

12.3 . Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics in the form of means and standard deviations for all variables and for the responses of all respondents were computed. Computed means signifies levels of agreeableness and disagreeableness of the respondents. Whereas the values of standard deviation serve as fundamental measures of variability. Computations of means and standard deviations are presented in table (8).

Table(8): Rates of Training and Development Types on Employees Performance and Productivity

Training Methods				Development Methods			
Section	Description	Mean	SD	Section	Description	Mean	SD
2	On Job Training	4.68	0.563	3	Formal Education Programs	4.32	0.546
	Off Job Training	4.42	0.524		Behavioral & Self assessment Programs	3.99	0.602
	Orientation & Induction	4.12	0.502		Enrich Job Experience	4.56	0.560
	Technical Training Programs	3.98	0.621		Scheduled Effective Feedback	4.03	0.556
	Foundation Training Programs	3.64	0.612		Train The Trainers Programs	3.65	0.610
	Refresher Training Programs	3.66	0.622		Enhancement & Job Satisfaction Program	3.77	0.620
	Health & Safety Training Programs	4.26	0.512		Effective Participation in Setting Development Programs	3.63	0.619
	Promotional & Advancement Training Programs	4.34	0.522		Career Development & Progression Programs	4.24	0.514
	Remedial Training Programs	3.87	0.608		Development Of Leadership Traits	3.61	0.604
	Field Training Programs	3.14	0.688		Membership Of Work & Professional Committees	3.52	0.602
--				Simulation & Special Assignments	3.34	0.689	
--				Job Rotation & Challenging Job Transfers	4.28	0.520	
Performance				Productivity			
Section	Description	Mean	SD	Section	Description	Mean	SD
4	Result –Oriented Measures (Criterion –Based): a) Effectiveness b) Efficiency c) Economy d) Quality	4.33	0.583	5	Improved Quality: d) Project e) Products f) Service	4.48	0.502
	Relative-Normative Measures: a) Concepts b) Instruments c) Applications	3.99	0.614		Less Defects, Failure & Malfunctions	4.22	0.511
	Predetermined Standards: a) Accuracy b) Completeness c) Cost d) Speed	4.13	0.506		Reduction of Staff Turnover & Absenteeism	4.06	0.545
					Minimum Control and Supervision needs	3.55	0.601
					Opportunity For Growth & Progress	3.76	0.618
					Improved Employees Behavior	3.58	0.623
					Competitive Edge Attainment	4.04	0.535
					Good Customers Service	4.11	0.501
					Waste Reduction	3.89	0.618
					Improved Working Conditions	4.00	0.545
			Improved Company Image	3.65	0.623		

As per the answers of the respondents in table 8, regarding the impact of training and development on employees performance and productivity, the following ranking were noticed:

- a) Independent variable "training methods": on job training is the highest with a mean of 4.68 and standard deviation of 0.563. While off job training is the second with a mean of 4.42 and standard deviation of 0.524. Ranked thirdly is promotional & advancement training programs with a mean

of 4.34 and standard deviation of 0.522. Fourth in rank is health & safety training programs with a mean of 4.26 and standard deviation 0.512. Fifth in rank is orientation & induction with a mean of 4.12 and standard deviation of 0.502. The mean of other variable ranges from (3.14 to 3.98) and standard deviation ranges from (0.608 to 0.688) . These statistics show that majority of the respondents surveyed do agree on the statement that training has impact on employee performance and productivity.

- b) Independent variable "development methods": enrich job experience is the highest with a mean of 4.56 and standard deviation of 0.546. While formal education programs is the second with a mean of 4.32 and standard deviation of 0.546. Ranked thirdly is job rotation & challenging job transfers with a mean of 4.28 and standard deviation of 0.520. Fourth in rank is career development & progression programs with a mean of 4.24 and standard deviation 0.514. Fifth in rank is orientation & induction with a mean of 4.03 and standard deviation of 0.556. The mean of other variable ranges from (3.34 to 3.99) and standard deviation ranges from (0.689 to 0.602) . These statistics show that majority of the respondents surveyed do agree on the statement that development has impact on employee performance and productivity.
- c) Dependent variable "performance": result –oriented measures, i.e. criterion –based with elements (effectiveness, efficiency, economy and quality) is the highest with a mean of 4.33 and standard deviation of 0.583. While Predetermined Standards with elements (accuracy, completeness, cost and speed) is the second with a mean of 4.13 and standard deviation of 0.506. Ranked thirdly is relative-normative measures with elements (concepts, instruments and applications) with a mean of 3.99 and standard deviation of 0.614. These statistics show that majority of the respondents surveyed do agree on the statement that performance is influenced by training and development methods provided by their companies.
- d) Dependent variable "productivity": improved quality with elements (projects, products and services) is the highest with a mean of 4.48 and standard deviation of 0.502. While less defects, failure and malfunctions is the second with a mean of 4.22 and standard deviation of 0.511. Ranked thirdly is good customers Service with a mean of 4.11 and standard deviation of 0.501. Fourth in rank is reduction of staff turnover and absenteeism with a mean of 4.06 and standard deviation 0.545. Fifth in rank is competitive edge attainment with a mean of 4.04 and standard deviation of 0.535. Sixth in rank is improved working conditions with a mean of 4.00 and standard deviation of 0.545. The mean of other variable ranges from (3.55 to 3.89) and standard deviation ranges from (0.601 to 0.618) . These statistics show that majority of the respondents surveyed do agree on the statement that productivity is influenced by training and development methods provided by their companies.

Descriptive Statistics in the form of overall means and standard deviations for both independent and dependent variables for the respondents were also computed and presented in table (9).

Table(9): Over all means for Training, Development, Performance and Productivity

Variables	Means	Standard Deviations
Training Methods	4.01	0.577
Development Methods	3.95	0.587
Performance	4.15	0.568
Productivity	3.94	0.560

Table 9 above shows that the overall means for all variables ranged from a low value of 3.94 to a high value of 4.15. Results of descriptive statistics reveal that the impact of training and development is considerable. As can be seen from table 9, the means for both independent variables (training and development methods) are relatively high, and are above the mean value of first dependent variable (in this case employees performance); expressed in figures 4.01 and 3.95 >4.15; this indicates that over all employees performance

is influenced by training and developments methods used. The same can be said for the second dependent variable; here the means for both independent variables (training and development methods) are relatively high, and are a above the overall mean value of second dependent variable (in this case employees productivity); expressed in figures 4.01 and 3.95 > 3.94; this indicates that employees and organizational productivity are influenced by training and developments methods used.

12.4. Inferential Statistics

12.4. (a) Factor Analysis

Factor analysis were carried out before inferential analysis of the results on training and development as the independent variables and performance and productivity as the dependent variables. The purpose of such analysis is to describe variability among the observed theme and check for any correlated variables with the aim of reducing data that was found redundant. For the thirty six items analyzed as shown on table 10 all items scored more than 0.3 which is the minimum requirement for inclusion of variables into the final model as recommended by [74]. In line with this recommendation any item not scoring above 0.3 should be dropped from the model and not further analyzed. By application no item was declared redundant and therefore all items retained in the model and were further analyzed. Factor analysis are shown in table (10).

Table(10): Factor Analysis on Training, Development, Performance and Productivity

Items No	Variables Measures			
	Training Measures	Development Measures	Performance Measures	Productivity Measures
1	.745	.662	.782	.755
2	.721	.631	.743	.712
3	.699	.732	.765	.702
4	.711	.688	--	.684
5	.581	.543	--	.643
6	.701	.711	--	.675
7	.654	.654	--	.621
8	.552	.633	--	.521
9	.488	.445	--	.553
10	.375	.613	--	.621
11	--	.667	--	.559
12	--	.556	--	--

12.4. (b) Pearson Correlation Coefficient

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is a measure of the strength of the association between the two variables. according to the common practice used in research studies that normally include several variables, beyond knowing the means and standard deviations of the dependent and independent variables, the researcher would often like to know how one variable is related to another. While correlation could range between

-1.0 and+1.0, the researcher need to know if any correlation found between two variables is significant or not (i.e.; if it has occurred solely by chance or if there is a high probability of its actual existence). As for the information, both significance levels of $p=0.01$ and $p=0.05$ are generally accepted conventional levels in social sciences research. This indicates that 99 and 95 times out of 100, the researcher can be sure that there is a true or significant correlation between the two variables and there is only 1% or 5% chances that the relationship does not truly exist. The correlation matrix between dependent variable and independent variables are exhibited in table (11) below.

Table (11): Correlation Matrix for all variables involved

Variables	Performance	Productivity	Training	Development	Training & Development
Performance	1.00				
Productivity	.549	1.00			
Training	.595	.582	1.00		
Development	.567	.564	.579	1.00	
Training & Development	.649	.636	.568	.566	1.00

Table 11 above depicted positive correlation between training, development, training & development, employees performance and productivity. The following results were indicated:

- (a) regarding the correlation between training, development, training & development and employees performance. The highest positive correlation in this study was found between training & development and employees' performance ($r = .649, p < 0.01$). The second highest correlation was between training and employees performance ($r = .595, p < 0.01$) and the third highest correlation was found between development and employees performance ($r = .567, p < 0.01$) and finally, high correlation was noticed between productivity and employees performance ($r = .549, p < 0.01$). In other words, the results indicate that all these variables have significant correlation with employees performance.
- (b) regarding the correlation between training, development, training & development and productivity. The highest positive correlation in this study was found between training & development and productivity ($r = .636, p < 0.01$). The second highest correlation was between training and productivity ($r = .582, p < 0.01$). Finally, high correlation was noticed between development and productivity ($r = .564, p < 0.01$). In other words, the results indicate that all these variables have significant correlation with productivity.

Table (12): Coefficients for training, development, training & development and performance

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	.325	.392	.419	3.511	.001
Training	.629	.095	.572	7.143	.053
Development	.584	.075	.546	5.971	.036
Training & Development	.605	.056	.588	4.876	.043

Table 12 above shows the relationship between training, development, training & development and performance. The results depict that employees performance will be 0.325, a unit increase in training would lead to increase in employees performance by 0.629 units, a unit increase in development would lead to increase in employees' performance by 0.584 units, a unit increase in training & development would lead to increase in Employees' performance by 0.605 units. Training had the greatest effect on employees performance, followed by training & development. Development had reasonable effect on employees performance. At 5% level of significance and 95% level of confidence, training had 0.053 level of significance. Training & Development had 0.043 level of significance, and finally development had 0.036 level of significance. Hence the sequence of the most significant factors is training, followed by training & development and then development. All these variables were found significant and had positive impact on employees performance.

Table (13): Coefficients for training, development, training & development and Productivity

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	.218	.292	.408	3.511	.001
Training	.609	.083	.571	6.241	.049
Development	.524	.069	.556	5.881	.039
Training & Development	.585	.058	.587	4.426	.042

Table 13 above shows the relationship between training, development, training & development and productivity. The results depict that productivity will be 0.218, unit increase in training would lead to increase in productivity by 0.609 units, a unit increase in development would lead to increase in productivity by 0.524 units, a unit increase in training & development would lead to increase in productivity by 0.585 units. Training had the greatest effect on productivity, followed by training & development. Development had reasonable effect on productivity. At 5% level of significance and 95% level of confidence, training had 0.049 level of significance. training & development had 0.042 level of significance, and finally development had 0.039 level of significance. Hence the sequence of the most significant factors is training, followed by training & development and then development. All these variables were found significant and had positive impact on productivity.

12.4. (c) Regression Analysis (Hypothesis Testing)

Regression analysis is a statistical procedure used for estimating the strength of relationships amongst the independent and dependents variables [75] . In this study linear regression model is applied to test listed hypothesis.

12.4. c. 1 Training, Development, Training & Development and Performance

Table (13): Model Summary For Training, Development, Training & Development and Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error	(β) Beta	F Value	T Value	Sig Levels
(1) Training and Performance	.572	.331	.324	.956	.572	59.986	8.775	.000
(2) Development and Performance	.546	.312	.298	.919	.546	46.433	8.488	.000
(3) Training & Development and Performance	.588	.349	.336	.972	.588	62.876	9.264	.000

Note: The beta column indicates the value of standardized regression coefficient. Beta represents the effect that standard deviation difference in the independent variable would have on the dependent variable in standard deviation (the standardized scores of the dependent variable).

Table 13 has deflected the following regression analysis where:

Model (1): The value of R Square implies that 33% variation in the dependent variable (performance) is because of independent variable (training). The value of F (59) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that training causes 57% positive variation in employees performance, $t= 8.775$ and also $p<0.001$). So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between employees training and employees performance " is rejected and H_1 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between employees training and employees performance " is accepted.

Model (2): The value of R Square implies that 31% variation in the dependent variable (performance) is because of independent variable (development). The value of F (54) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that training causes 54% positive variation in employees performance, $t= 8.488$ and also $p<0.001$). So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between employees development and employees performance " is rejected and H_2 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between employees development and employees performance " is accepted.

Model (3): The value of R Square implies that 34% variation in the dependent variable (performance) is because of independent variable (training & development). The value of F (62) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that training & development causes 58% positive variation in employees performance, $t= 9.264$ and also $p<0.001$). So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between employees training & development and employees performance " is rejected and H_3 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between employees training & development and employees performance " is accepted.

12.4. c. 2 Training, Development, Training & Development and Productivity

Table (14): Model Summary For Training, Development, Training & Development and Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error	(β) Beta	F Value	T Value	Sig Levels
(4) Training and Productivity	.571	.329	.313	.947	.571	58.986	8.724	.000
(5) Development and Productivity	.556	.327	.309	.923	.556	49.433	8.635	.000
(6) Training & Development and Productivity	.587	.345	.338	.968	.587	61.776	9.164	.000

Note: The beta column indicates the value of standardized regression coefficient. Beta represents the effect that standard deviation difference in the independent variable would have on the dependent variable in standard deviation (the standardized scores of the dependent variable).

Model (4): The value of R Square implies that 32% variation in the dependent variable (productivity) is because of independent variable (training). The value of F (58) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that training causes 57% positive variation in productivity, $t=8.724$ and also $p<0.001$). So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between employees training and productivity " is rejected and H_4 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between employees training and productivity " is accepted.

Model (5): The value of R Square implies that 32% variation in the dependent variable (productivity) is because of independent variable (development). The value of F (49) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that development causes 55% positive variation in productivity, $t=8.635$ and also $p<0.001$. So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between development and productivity " is rejected and H_5 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between development and productivity " is accepted.

Model (6): The value of R Square implies that 34% variation in the dependent variable (productivity) is because of independent variable (training & development). The value of F (61) implies that the model possess significant overall strength. This ensures the correctness of the model. On the basis of Beta coefficients the model implies that training & development causes 58% positive variation in productivity, $t=9.164$ and also $p<0.001$. So H_0 which declares that "There is not a significance relationship between training & development and productivity " is rejected and H_6 which declares that "There is a significant relationship between training & development and productivity " is accepted.

13.1. Discussion of Findings

The general objective of this research was to assess the impact of training and development on employee's performance and productivity for the case of Jordanian private sector transportation companies located in the southern region of Jordan. Most of the respondents through their answers confirmed the important role of training and development on their performance and productivity. According to responses training and development methods and activities brought new potentials for employees when performing task and resulted in increased performance and productivity. Descriptive statistics in the form of means as listed previously in table 8 provide evidence that training and development are essential key variables that definitely lead to enhancement in performance and increased productivity. Toward a better understanding of the effects of training and development in chosen companies, this research points out the importance of training and development for the workforce, determines the major types of training and development programs, discusses the extent of relationship that exist between training and development and decide the overall impact on employees performance, productivity, and over all organizational performance. Also offers some guidelines for human resource managers to design effective and diversified programs for training and development. This is in line with the view of [76]. They suggested that methods of training and development of workers include on-the-job-training and off-the-job training such as; apprenticeship, demonstration, orientation, coaching and so on. Their study further revealed that job instruction, delegation, special projects, group discussion, programmed instructions, simulation conferences, case study, role playing, lecturing, job rotation and so on, were also among the methods of training and development of manpower used by organizations for effective and upgraded organizational performance. In agreement with read literature the selection of such methods is commonly used because these methods are tested and found reliable for increased productivity and self-reliance if practiced fully by the organization.

Inferential statistics, on the other hand generated tabulated statistics that shows the results of correlations, coefficients and regressions on the data collected from 188 respondents through questionnaires. After applying the linear regression on the collected data to check the cause and effect relationship between the training and development (independent variable) and employees performance and productivity (dependent variables) the above mentioned result has been drawn. The probability of f-statistic shows the significance level of the research. According to the standard if the p value is < 0.05 so than it is significant. In this study the above given tables demonstrates the p value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 thus the model of the research is statistically significant. So the independent variable of the study, training and development, has significant relationship with dependant variable of the study, employees performance and productivity. Finally, the standardized values of the above mentioned tables illustrate obviously that independent variable training and development have a positive impact on employees performance and productivity in this study.

The findings of this study is supporting to other research papers on training and development. In line with this study is [77] it was established from their study that there is a strong positive relationship between training and performance. Training generates benefits for the employee knowledge, skills, ability, competences and behavior. From the findings most respondents strongly agreed that training develops skills and competences to improve performance, it reduces learning time for employees starting new jobs on appointment, transfer or promotion and training helps to reconcile the gap between what should happen and what is happening to increase the level of performance. According to [78], training has significant impact and positive relationship with employee performance and developments areas. They also added that this would be helpful for human resources professionals in pharmaceutical industry in Karachi Pakistan to understand and knows the importance of the impact that training improves employee's performance in different performance & development areas, working in various departments of pharmaceutical companies in Karachi. Hence from the above discussion training is considered as most important practice that cannot be discarded form an organizations because the more the employee gets training, the more efficient their level of performance would be. Study results of [79] showed that training and development, on the job training, training design and delivery style have significant affects on employee performance and organizational performance. They concluded that effective and careful provision of training and development increases the overall organizational performance. In line with above research is [80]. Here The main finding of this research shows that training and development have a positive correlation on the outputs of employee's performance and effectiveness. This relationship was tested for causality using linear regression statistical model and found out employee effectiveness has a direct cause and effect relationship with employee performance, and training and development.

Further studies, like [81] confirmed that the relationships proposed among the variables in the research model were tested and it was found that relationship exists amongst the variables having subjected the collected data to empirical analysis with the use of descriptive statistics. The results of the findings indicated that training and development affects employees performance and organizational effectiveness, which implies that effort must be made to ensure that employees skills and knowledge are fully underutilized through adequate and timely training design and implementation. They also concluded that training is importation for the survival of any organization. It is also imperative for effective performance of employees, enhancement of employees' ability to adapt to the changing and challenging business environment and technology for better performance, increase employees knowledge to develop creative and problem solving skills. In a similar view [82] the results of the study showed that organizational performance depends largely on manpower training and development. In view of this, the researchers recommend that business organizations should have regular and well-thought out training and development programs for their employees. Such programs should be capable of raising the skills, morale and productivity of employees . Indeed, the researchers also called for the involvement of experts in the design and implementation of manpower training and development programs in the organization. According to them engaging employees, management and experts in such actions will avoid wastes, both in terms of time and resources, by providing what is actually needed and very relevant to the needs of the employees. When this is done, the objectives of manpower training and development will be realized, thus repositioning the organization at the level of higher performance.

13.2.Manegerial and Practical Implications

Human resources are regarded as the most vital assets of the organization, therefore careful management approach is required to get advantages of this valuable resource. This research emphasized the importance of providing effective methods of training and development in an attempt to increase employees performance and productivity. In real life concerns employers must provide their employees with opportunities to improve their foundational skills so as to enable them to cope with more complex situations. In order to do so, employers must align training and development needs with business objectives. Alignment absence will fail training and development programs intensions. In this respect it worth noting that organizations who meet their needs for training in an ad hoc, irrational and haphazard way will design unplanned and

unsystematic methods of training and development. Management at all levels must understand the fact that training and development are important tools that allow organizations to gain competitive advantages and to compete with the changing and competitive business world. It is therefore strongly recommended that all owners, directors, senior managers, junior managers, supervisors and the employees should be involved in one way or the other in training and development as there is a positive relationship of training and performance to enhance employee knowledge, skills, ability, competencies and behavior. The practical approach of support and involvement should be used if training and development goal to be achieved. This study helps organization to understand the importance of training and development; to understand which factors are important to keep in mind during the training and how a good training can be delivered to their employees. The study will help the organizations to understand that it is very necessary for them to give training to their employees so that they could perform the assign task in a better way. Although understanding of the said issues is critical, yet it is not enough alone. Management must facilitate the transfer of learning, be available to give support before and after employee training and provide continuous effective feedback during and after training and developments sessions. In practice, advanced human capital management is imperative for building modern organizations with strong stands for survival and long existence. This can be achieved by requiring human resource professionals to develop strategies that will ensure superior knowledge, skills and experience to settle within the workforce. Here those persons selected for delivering training should be well trained in this field, and know how to meet with hope as well as necessities of the employees. Practically, the study confirms that employees demands must be fulfilled with respect to training; so the interdependence of training and performance are poorly distressed. Employees who are committed in their jobs, profession and careers want to know more about their company and industry and to learning those skills that will improve their overall performance.

14.1. Conclusions

Findings of this study and supporting findings from large number of reviewed research papers reveal that training and development has positive relationship and strong positive impact on employees performance and productivity. Respondents across studied companies showed high agreement on the statement that the use of different methods of training and developments is beneficial not only to them but also for the organization as well. Benefits are obvious if training programs and development plans are devised which fit the trainees, the job description, the managers and supervisors and their different levels of education and background appropriately and go in line with companies goals and objectives. Therefore Investing in training and development is imperative for any organization, which will certainly realize returns on its investment in training and developing its workers. Return forms include: long-term increase in productivity and to an increase in quality as a result of potentially fewer mistakes. Moreover, effective development programs allow for the organization to maintain a workforce that can adequately replace employees who may leave the company or who are moved to other areas. On the individual level employees are encouraged to carry out self-assessment, where they are expected to identify their opportunities and needs for improvement.

Furthermore, findings revealed that on the job training is very effective and it also saves time and cost. Training and development, on the job training, training design and delivery style have significant effect on both employees performance and productivity and all these have positively affected companies performance by increasing it. It was evident from respondents replies that participation and cooperation between managers and employees is necessary to produce maximum impact reflected in the form of increased performance. Achieving that requires mutual efforts; managers should identify only those employee development programs that are central and can add value to the organization and employees who are developed must be given the requisite resources to work with and the necessary management or leadership support to enable them to translate their new skills acquired from the development programs into initiatives and action that can benefit the organization. On the basis of respondent's answers of transportation companies one can make the conclusion that training cannot be discarded from the industry; and the companies have to set up and implement an advanced roadmap for training and development as it enhances employee performance. Main elements of such map include proper systematic identification of the training

needs and skill deficit of employees, monitor and evaluate with objective tools or criteria and provide effective feedback so as the program outcomes help to maximize the impact of training and development activities in these companies. The study also concluded that first line managers have responsibility to make strategic decisions regarding the types of training and development that contribute positively towards employees performance, productivity and organizational performance. Finally, the researcher can conclude that training and development programs are very much important in order to achieve excellence and competencies in knowledge, skills, ability, potential, attitude and behavior so than to meet rapid changes in technology and changes in work practices.

14.2.Recommendations

Since the relationship between training , development and employees performance and productivity is affirmed to be strong and positive, then the researcher is in an position to give the following recommendations as per the findings of the study:

14.2.1.Recommendations for employers

1. In order training to play a positive role in the organization the policies about training and development should be, clear, objective, simple and should be communicated to the trainees.
2. Employers, managers and decision makers should endeavor to create enabling training environment and favorable training policies that will give every worker opportunity to attend training. Management should also take into consideration the training need of each workers and act as appropriate.
3. The employer should have compulsory training programs for all employees in order to improve the knowledge and understanding of annual business strategy and objectives.
4. The employer should provide improved working conditions so that they become conducive to the transfer of learning. They should also provide sufficient resources for training so as to improve the training programs provided.
5. The employer should provide mixed and diversified methods of training and development so that employees acquire knowledge, skills and ability from different sources and in different delivery styles.
6. The employer should design strategies pertains to training and development of employees in their organization and before carrying out the training programs. These strategic approaches should be adopted to ensure that training programs are consistent with the overall objectives of the organizations.
7. Designed strategies on training and development must take into account the following important factors: changes in the business environment, changes in technology, consistency with the overall objectives of the organizations, training needs and solutions, regularity and levels of training, cost and benefits, time and so on.
8. Quality and relevant training and development programs should be organized by organizations in away to meet up with employees' expectation or improved productivity.
9. On-the-Job methods of manpower training and development are highly recommended to organizations. These methods ensure that there is no loss of man hours as a result of off-the-job trainings where employees travel out of the country or out of station to tour around.

14.2.2.Recommendations for Employees

1. Employees should comprehend the significance of training and development programs to enhance their professional skills and ability.
2. Employees should participate actively and enthusiastically in training and development activities to strengthen their skills and knowledge
3. Employees should know the importance of their competence in skills and enhancement of knowledge along with motivation and active participation in training programs because that would give benefits to employees as well the organization.

4. Employees should be provided with more and continuous training programs in order to reduce the cost of recruiting and training new staff members.
5. Employees should be provided with effective feedback after training is in order for employees to become aware of areas where they can best improve their performance.
6. Employees should be provided with effective training and development in order to reduce the cost and time spent by managers on supervising employees.
7. Employees should take advantage of all self-development opportunities provided to them by the organizations through easy access of resources and facilities so that they become a knowledge-based persons. Developing the employee in such manner not only increase the productivity of organization, it also upgrade the employees' skills and equipped them for the future challenges.
8. Employees should always identify their aspirations and abilities, and through counseling recognize what training and development are required for a particular career information and training. Here development and succession planning will also play a great role. Career progressions projection plans and training and development projections should be made available to each employee so that they know exactly their contribution to organization and its overall performance.

14.2.3. Recommended Effective and Well Structured Training Process

Training is a circular process that begins with needs identification and after a number of steps ends with the provision of effective feedback. The researcher confirms that if the following steps are followed systematically and patiently then end results would be satisfactory to participants and to organization as well . The following illustrate these steps:

1. **Identification of training needs:** Training need is a condition where there is a gap between "what is" and "what should be" in terms of incumbents' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behavior for a particular situation at one point in time. This gap is called "a problem," which usually occurs when a difference exists between "desired performance" and "actual performance." The needs identification process assists trainers in making sure that they have matched a training program to a training problem.
2. **Analyzing organizations training needs:** Training needs and organizational objectives should be parallel to each other. The results of these analyses are then compared with the objectives of the organization. These comparisons point to specific areas in which training is needed.
3. **Formulate training objectives:** Objectives should be SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Timely) and unambiguous, and should develop individual as well as meet the needs of organizations. Objectives should also include performance targets, measures standards and should be seen as attainable by individuals.
4. **Review already existing training methods:** Reviewing should include elements like: convenience, content, delivery style and depth of information.
5. **Use present methods or alternatively develop new ones:** When selecting employee training and development methods, it is important to remember that training and development is a learning process. Employee training and development needs to suit your organization's context, job descriptions, employment contracts and collective agreements.
6. **Implement the training program developed:** Once the planning phase of a training program is complete, then it is time to implement the course. Implementation is the point where a trainer activates the training plan, or it is the process of putting a training program into operation.
7. **Evaluate training and developments methods used:** Evaluation is a process to determine the relevance, effectiveness, and impact of activities in light of their objectives. In evaluating an extension training program, one needs to consider that most training activities exist in a larger context of projects, programs, and plans. Evaluation results can be used for further decision making.
8. **Measure the obtained results against standards:** Individual, group and organizational standards are commonly used by today's organizations. Results are concerned with the tangible impact of the training program on individuals, their job environment, or the organization as a whole.

- 9. Give effective feedback to participants:** Effective and timely feedback is a critical component of a successful training and development program and should be used in conjunction with setting performance goals. If effective feedback is given to employees on their progress towards their goals, employee performance will improve. People need to know in a timely manner how they're doing, what's working, and what's not. Feedback can come from many different sources: managers and supervisors, measurement systems, peers, and so on.

15. 1.Limitations of the Study

Similar to other research studies, this study has the following prominent limitations: Firstly, the study is limited to the influence of two independent variables namely training and development. Based on this limitation, it is recommended that future research could include additional variables such as empowerment, capabilities..etc that correspondingly donate to performance and productivity which the existing research cannot conceal . Secondly, the measurement of study variables and their effect on performance and productivity are all based on respondents perceptions and attitudes while filling the questionnaires. Thus, elements of errors and bias might exist in the data set. Thirdly, the study covered only six transportation companies in the private sector, so if findings of this study to be generalized, then public sector transportation companies should be researched to get more updated valuable contributions regarding the effect of training and development on employees performance and productivity. Fourthly, the overall findings of this study is applicable to smaller to medium sized companies, therefore, the present findings cannot be generalized to bigger firms. Fifthly, despite the fact that the literature search was extensive, potentially valuable studies may not have been included and the selection of literature sources may have elements of bias and subjectivity. Finally, the sample size is relatively small for such kind of study this is due to time, resources and willingness to respond constraints. Regarding the willingness to respond the researcher assured respondents that the confidentiality of the information provided will be maintained and such information will only be used for the study purpose. Finally the study used only quantitative approach to find answer to questions through analysis of quantitative data, i.e., the data shown in figures and numbers. Qualitative research methodology on the other hand can help researchers approach fieldwork without being constrained by any predetermined categories of analysis, i.e. qualitative research carries the uniqueness because it does not give conclusion in advance, therefore qualitative research can be used in foreseeable future research.

15. 2.Future Research Directions

This study concluded a noticeable positive relationship in between employees training , development and employee performance and productivity. However, there still numerous other variables that might be playing role in this particular field so, it's going to be very beneficial for researchers should they conduct research in this particular field in foreseeable future by including additional variables like employee capabilities, employees involvement, employee satisfaction, employee inspiration, employee motivation and organization effectiveness along with other working condition in relation to employees training and development to create more convincing results that may increase the incredible importance of employee training and development. Forthcoming researchers are intensely stimulated to empirically assess more advanced models of training and development in diverse executive situations/frameworks. For instance, investigate the effect of management development instead of employee development on organizational performance. Such studies should exceed operatives and junior employees to higher levels of management.

Acknowledgement

I am so grateful to the management of transportation companies for their permission and support given to me in the data collection and in many other respects. Sincere thanks are also extended to all study participants for their time and participation in filling questionnaires. May God Almighty bless us all.

References used

1. Abdus Sattar Niazi (2011), "Training and Development Strategy and Its Role in Organizational Performance" *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, ISSN 2161-7104, 2011, Vol.1, No.2, pp.42-57. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v1i2.862>.
2. Tannenbaum, S., J. Mathieu, E. Salas and J. Cannon- Bowers. (1991). Meeting trainee's expectations: the influence of training fulfillment on the development of commitment, self-efficacy, and motivation, *J. App. Psychol.* 76(6): 759-769.
3. Armstrong, M. (2006) *Strategic Human Resource Management: A Guide to Action*. Kogan Page, London
4. Haunstein, N.M.H. (1998) Training Raters to Increase the Accuracy of Appraisals and the Usefulness of Feedback. in Smither, J.W. (Eds.), *Performance Appraisal: State of the Art in Practice*, Jossey-Bass. San Francisco
5. Drummond, H. (2000). *Effective Management: A hand book for manager*. Kogan Page.
6. Shen, J. (2004) *International Training and Management Development: Theory and Reality: A Conceptual Study*. *Journal of Management Development*, 24, 656-666. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02621710510608786>
7. Cole G. A (2002): *Personnel Management Theory and Practice*; London; East Wilts Educational.
8. Ivancevich T. M Lorenzi P, Skinner S. J and Crosby, P. B (1994): *Management Quality and Competitiveness*; Illinois: Irwin Publishers.
9. Cole G. A (2002): *Personnel Management Theory and Practice*; London; East Wilts Educational.
10. Muo, I. K. (2007): *Change Management & Change Agents: Classifications, Responsibilities & Critical Success Factors*; *Babcock Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, Vol. 5. N0. 2. January
11. Wikipedia (2010): *The Free Encyclopedia*, [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/human capital](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/human%20capital).
12. Neelam Tahir, and Others (2014) " The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity :A case study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan" *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences* April 2014, Vol. 4, No. 4. pp.86-98.
13. Becker, K., Antuar, N., and Everett, C. (2011). *Implementing an Employee Performance Management System in a Nonprofits Organization*. *Nonprofits Management and Leadership*. 21(3), 255-271
14. Okoh, A. (2005): *Personnel: The Management of People at Work*. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co.
15. Sims, R. (2002). *Organizational Success through Effective Human Resources Management*. Westport CT: Quorum Books.
16. Sims, R. S. (2006). *Human Resource Development: Today and Tomorrow*. IAP.
17. McDowall, A. and Saunders, M.N.K. (2010) *UK Manager's Conceptions of Training and Development*. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 34, 609-630. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/03090591011070752>
18. Khan, R.A.G., Khan, F.A. and Khan, M.A. (2011) *Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11, 62-68.
19. Braga, C.A.P. (1996) *The Impact of the Internationalization of Services on Developing Countries*. *Finance and Development*, 33, 34-37.
20. Beardwell, N. and Holden, B. (1993) *Managing for Success*. 2nd Edition, Prentice Hall Publisher, England.
21. Saleem, Q., Shahid, M. & Naseem, A. 2011. Degree of influence of training and development on employee's behavior. *International Journal of Computing and Business Research*, 2(3): 2229-6166.
22. Laing, I. F. 2009. *The impact of training and development on work performance and productivity in public sectors organizations: A case study of Ghana ports and Garbous authority*. A thesis submitted to Institute of Distance Learning, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science, and Technology.
23. Singh, R. & Mohanty, M. 2012. *Impact of Training Practices on Employee Productivity: A Comparative Study*. *Inter science Management Review*, 2(2): 2231-1513.
24. Barzegar, N. & Shahroz, F. 2011. *A Study on the Impact of on the job training Courses on the Staff Performance (A Case Study)*. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29 (2011) : 1942 – 1949

25. Blain, J. (2009) Current Learning Trends in Europe and the United States. (online)<https://cdns3.trainingindustry.com/media/2505191/cegocurrent%20learning%20trends%20in%20eu%20and%20us>.
26. Grobler, P., Warnich, S., Carrell, M.R., Elbert, N.F. and Hatfield, R.D. (2006) Human resource management in South Africa. (3rdEd). South Africa: Thompson Learning.
27. McConnell, R.C. (2004). Managing employee performance. Journal of Health Care Management, 23(3):273–283.
28. Amir Elnaga, Amen Imran. (2012), The Effect of Training on Employee Performance, European Journal of Business and Management, Vol.5.
29. Miller A. J., Sphr, Osinski M. D., SPHR.(1996), Training needs assessment.
30. Mehrdad, A., Mahdi, S., Ali, S.: A Study of on the Job Training Effectiveness: Empirical Evidence of Iran. In: International Journal of Business and Management, Vol. 4(2009), No. 11, p. 63-68.
31. Mahbuba Sultana (2013) 'Impact of Training in Pharmaceutical Industry: An Assessment on Square Pharmaceuticals Limited, Bangladesh', International Journal of Science and Research , 2(2), pp. 576-587.
32. James Onyango and Daniel M. Wanyoike (2014)" effects of training on employees performance : Asurvey of health workers in Siaya county Kenya" European Journal of Material Sciences, Vol.1, No 1.March 2014, pp.11-15.
33. Ms. Pallavi P. Kulkarni.(2013): A literature review on training and development and quality of work. International Refereed Research Journal www.researchersworld.com Vol.–IV, Issue–2, April 2013.
34. <http://www.hrware.com/general-hr/training-development/>
35. Ekpo A. N (1989): Manpower Development In Nigeria: In S C Ogbuagu (ed) Strategy for National Development In Nigeria : Calabar: University of Calabar Press p 143-154
36. Drucker P. F. (1999): Management Challenges for the First Century, New York. Hoper Business.
37. Lawal M. M (2006): Manpower Management; A Hand Book for Personnel Managers and Students of Administration. Abuja, Roots Books and Journal Nigeria Limited.
38. Adeniyi O. I (1995): Staffing Training and Development: in Ejiogu, A; Achumba, I. New Ed. Enugu: Asika Publications.
39. Oshionebo, B. O. (2003): Dimensions of Management and Organizational Management; Ibadan, Spetrum Books.
40. Aswathappa, K. (2000), "Human resource and Personnel Management", Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi.
41. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/effects-training-development-employee-performance-ackah-ph-d>
42. <http://essaymonster.net/business/111033-training-and-development-systems-and-practices.html>
43. Malone, V. M, (1984), "Inservice training and staff development", Agricultural extension: A reference manual, Rome: FAO, pp.12
44. Armstrong Michael, (2000), "Understanding training", Human Resource Management Practice, 8th Edition, Kogan page limited, London pp:543
45. Birdi, K., Clegg, C., Patterson, M. Robinson, A., Stride, C. B., Wall, T.D. Wood, S. J. (2008): The impact of human resource and operational management practices on company productivity: a longitudinal study. In: Personnel Psychology, , vol. 61, no. 3.p. 467-501.
46. Kennedy, P.E, Chyung, S.Y. Winiecke D.J., Brinkerholff, R.O (2013): Training professionals' usage and understanding of Kirkpatrick's Level 3 and Level 4 evaluations. In: International Journal of Training and Development, 18:1.
47. Onuka, A.O.U. & Ajaya, Kassimo (2012): effects of manpower development on workers job performance. European Journal of Educational Studies 4(3), 2012, Ocean Publication.

48. Oguntimehin, A. (2001): "Teacher Effectiveness: Some practical Strategies for Successful implementation of Universal Basic Education in Nigeria" African Journal of Educational Management Vol. 9, No 1 P. 151 – 161
49. <http://essaymonster.net/business/108219-training-and-development-in-todays-business.html>
50. Nel, P., Gerber, P., van Dyk, P., Haasbroek, D., Schultz, H., Sono, T. and Werner, A. (2004). Human resources management (6thEd) South Africa: Oxford University Press.
51. Robbins, S.P., Odendaal, A. and Roodt, G. (2003) Organizational behavior: Global and Southern African perspectives. South Africa: Pearson Education.
52. Perry, B. (2007). Organizational management and information systems Oxford: Elsevier.
53. Kleiman, L.S. (2003). Human resource management (3rdEd) USA: Atomic Dog.
54. Manu, J. S. (2004). "Training and development techniques for improving organizational performance for Ghanaian firms". The Graduate School, University of Wisconsin-Stout , pp.1-43.
55. Cooke F L., (2000), Human Resource Strategy to improve Organizational Performance: A route for British firms, Working Paper No 9 EWERC, Manchester School of Management.
56. Rothwell, W.J. and Kazanas, H.C. (2006). Planning and managing human resources (2nd Ed) Mumbai: Jaico.
57. Khawaja Fawad Latif, Shahid Jan, Nasir Shaheen (2013), ' Association of Training Satisfaction with Employee Development aspect of Job Satisfaction' Journal of Managerial Sciences, Volume 162 VII Number 1
58. <http://www.referenceforbusiness.com/management/Pr-Sa/Productivity-Concepts-and-Measures.html>
59. Nel, P., Gerber, P., van Dyk, P., Haasbroek, D., Schultz, H., Sono, T. and Werner, A. (2004). Human resources management (6thEd) South Africa: Oxford University Press.
60. H. Singh, (2012). Training and development: A prominent determinant for improving HR productivity". International Conference on Management and education innovation IPEDR 37: 274 – 278
61. Graig, P. (1996): Skill training and work organization in American establishment. Industrial Relations, 34 (2), 125-146.
62. Nankervis, A. R., Compton, R. L., and McCarthy, T. E.(1999). Strategic Human Resource Management,(3rd Ed.), Nelson ITP, Melbourne.
63. Nwachukwu, S. (1992): The Crisis of Development in Africa: The Democratic Imperatives. Journal of Social Development, 1(4), 84-87.
64. Akinpoju, B. (1999): "Educational Technology and teaching – learning process in the 21st century" in Adesomowo, P.O. (Ed), Basic of Education, Lagos Triumph Books publishers.
65. Kayode, T. (2001): "The Role of Training in charge Management" Journal of the Institute of Personnel Management of Nigeria. Vol. 10, No 7 PP. 24 – 31.
66. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2003). Research methods for business students (3rdEd) Harlow, England: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
67. Gay, L. R. (2005) Educational Research: Competencies for Analysis and Applications (8 th Edition), London
68. Kothari, C. K. (2011) Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques (2nd Revised Edition) New Age International Publishers, New Delhi
69. Kerlinger, F.N. & H.B. Lee, (2000, 4th Ed). Foundations of behavioral research. Wadsworth.
70. Mugenda, O. M. and Abel G. Mugenda, A. G. (2008) Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches: Nairobi, African Centre for Technology Studies.
71. Mullins, L.J. (2005). Management and organizational behavior (7th Ed) Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
72. Franklin Kum, Richard Cowden and Anis Karod. (2014) "The impact of training and development on employee performance" a case study of Escon Consulting, Singaporean Journal Of Business, Economics and, Management studies Vol.3, no.3, 2014.pp 72-105.

73. Cooper, R. D., and Shindler, S. P. (2007). Business research methods, (9th Ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
74. Hair, J.F., Anderson, R.E., Tatham, R.L., & Black, W.C. (2010). Multivariate Data Analysis, Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River, NJ
75. David M. Lane. Introduction to Linear Regression. Available from: <http://onlinestatbook.com/2/regression/intro.html>.
76. Ewuim N. C and Ubochi I (2007): Principles of Personnel Management in Nigeria Lagos: Dominica Publishers.
77. W. Dabale, N. Jagero and M. Nyauchi (2014) " The Relationship between Training and Employee Performance" The Case of Mutare City Council, Zimbabwe. International Journal of Human Resource Studies, 2014, Vol. 4, No. 4, pp 61-72.
78. U. Hafeez and W. Akbar (2015) "Impact of Training on Employees Performance" Evidence from Pharmaceutical Companies in Karachi, Pakistan. Business Management and Strategy, Vol. 6, No. 1
79. Raja Khan, Furqan Khan, and Muhammad. Khan,(2011), " Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance" Global Journal of Management and Business Research, Volume 11, Issue 7, Version 1.0
- 80.A. Asfaw, M. Argaw and L. Bayissa,(2015) "The Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance and Effectiveness" A Case Study of District Five Administration Office, Bole Sub-City, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies, Vol. 3, 188-202
81. H. Falola, A. Osibaanjo and S.Ojo,(2014) "effectiveness of training and development on employees performance and organizations competitiveness in the Nigerian Banking Industry" Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov Series V: Economic Sciences. Vol. 7 (56) No. 1
82. S. Aigbepue and E. Mammud,(2012), " training, development and organizational performance" JORIND 10 (3), December. ISSN 1596 - 8308. www.transcampus.org./journals, www.ajol.info/journals/jorind